

HOW DO BORROWED WORDS AFFECT THE ORIGINAL LANGUAGE?

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У заимствований долгая история, и они влияют не только на язык, но и на самих людей и культуру. Иногда даже носители языка не смогут определить, что определенное слово на самом деле заимствовано из другого языка. Но полезно ли это? Это важный вопрос с точки зрения филологии.

Abstract

Borrowings have a long history and affect not only the language, but also the people and culture themselves. Sometimes even native speakers can't identify that the word is actually borrowed from another language. But is it useful or harmful? From the point of view of philology, this is an important question.

Ключевые слова: филология, заимствования, язык...

Keywords: philology, borrowings, language...

The relevance of this topic is that the borrowing of words has been going on for a long time, it is a constant process. And this process has both advantages and disadvantages.

The purpose of my article is to analyze the impact of such words on the language; to identify the consequences, pros or cons, using a specific example in the form of statistics.

As **the tasks** of my work, I want to highlight a complete analysis of the influence of borrowed words on the Russian language, the opinion of interviewed on this matter.

Content

To begin with, it is worth answering the question: why did borrowings appear in the language? Several reasons can be noted:

1) There is no suitable word in the language to describe a phenomenon or object. For example, the Japanese word "karaoke" has been borrowed into many languages, but it does not have a single analogue.

2) The status of the language from which the word is borrowed. Thus, borrowed words compete with existing ones or even become more widely used among people. For example, the English word "skipper" and the Russian word "шкипер" were borrowed from the Danish language (schipper) during the heyday of the Danish navy.

3) Some borrowed words can more accurately describe a phenomenon or object or be more pleasant to use. Word "killer" was borrowed from English to Russian language instead of the Russian word

"убийца", because the killer is a more narrowly focused concept, denoting a professional killer with a firearm, but it also sounds more pleasant than "убийца" in Russian.

4) Some single words can replace whole phrases of the original language. For example, the word "sprint" from English replaces the phrase "short distance running" from Russian, which is more convenient to use for people.

However, not all countries are open to new "foreign" words. Many states struggle with borrowing words from other languages because they "pollute" the native one. New bills are being created to preserve the language, and a lot of money is being spent. For example, in France there is a law that says that it is forbidden to use any foreign words (for trademarks, etc.) if there are French analogues.

However, these measures can also be explained by the fact that French people dislike the British. We are used to seeing England and France as allies during wars, but this was not always the case. In the XIX century, Napoleon saw a powerful opponent in England, fought with it, created all sorts of restrictions. Apparently, this fact has been preserved in the national consciousness.

At the moment, the record language for borrowing is English. So many words have been borrowed into many other languages because English has become an international language of communication. People started traveling, using the Internet and doing business,

and in all aspects English is an integral part. In my opinion, stopping the flow of borrowing in the era of globalization is a very difficult task.

Language is a flexible system that can easily change under the influence of other languages, this is a natural process. Now English language is beginning to "capture" Russian. Of course, it was like that before. For example, previously most words in Russia were borrowed from French, as it was fashionable for aristocrats.

Nowadays people can say something and not even understand that the word is not native Russian, it no longer hurts the ear. In my opinion, the main reason is the Internet. The Internet is the most widespread system in almost all spheres of human activity. It is worth noting that it is also very fast, so words can appear at lightning speed, and people don't even notice how the language is changing. A lot of borrowed words are used in the IT sphere, which is becoming more and more popular every day.

Let's look at people's opinions on the pros and cons of borrowing: more than half, according to statistics, tend to believe that borrowing is beneficial. As the main advantages they note:

borrowed words make the native language richer, help it develop;

it facilitates communication between people who speak different languages;

students learning English can master the language faster.

But there are also those who disagree with this. The main disadvantages are:

the original language loses its identity, borrowings displace existing synonyms;

this is an irreversible process;
the meaning of such words is not clear to everyone.

Conclusion

Each language is unique and interesting in its own way. However, the process of borrowing cannot be stopped, vocabulary is the most mobile, used and flexible layer in people's lives. We study foreign languages, communicate with any person in any country, travel the world and use the Internet. Therefore, the question of the benefits or harms of borrowing is still very difficult.

On the one hand, it has become much easier and more comfortable to communicate around the world, the native language is self-developing, and new phenomena can be given a name. On the other hand, how to prevent the loss of identity? Why do people use borrowings, if the language has its own analogues? Right now, in the era of technology and simplified communication, this problem is more relevant than ever.

Summing up, I can highlight that it is impossible to prohibit borrowing. In my opinion, it is necessary to use them correctly and appropriately, without giving priority if there are suitable synonyms in the language.

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